

Technical Guidelines for Weighting in GGS-II

Instructions for National Teams

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Introduction

In analysing GGS-II data, an important issue is whether, and if so, how, to account for (1) the sampling design that has been used to collect the data and (2) selective response (Biemer & Christ, 2008).

In these guidelines, we provide an overview of how weighting has to be dealt with in the GGS-II and what the roles of National Teams and the Central Hub are in this regard. Our approach is strongly inspired by the way these aspects are handled in the ESS Round 9 (Kaminska, 2020). Therefore, we will first discuss the approach taken by the ESS, followed by an overview of how we are going to apply this approach in the GGS and what is expected of National Teams and the Central Hub.

In an Appendix, an empirical example based on ESS Round 9 of the consequences of (not) taking the sampling design and weighting into account is provided.

Handling Sampling Features in the European Social Survey Round 9

In ESS Round 9, country-specific information on sampling design and other relevant issues is provided in so-called ‘National Technical Summaries’ that are included in the ESS9 – 2018 Documentation Report compiled by the ESS Data Archive (2018). Each NTS includes information on the data collector and funder, sampling design, fieldwork characteristics, response rates, weighting and coding issues. Together, this documentation provides a comprehensive overview of how data collection has occurred in the participating countries.

In addition, the ESS has included a number of variables in the released datasets that can be used in analyses to take the sampling design, differences in sampling inclusion probabilities and differences in response between relevant groups into account. How to use these variables is described in a separate document (Kaminska, 2020).

In general, three elements are important to take into account:

1. Clustering and stratification
2. Selection probabilities
3. Selective response

Sampling theory states that simple random sample (SRS) is the most efficient way of sampling respondents for a survey, as the selection probability of each member of the population is the same. However, for all kinds of reasons, the actual sampling design may differ from the SRS.

Stratification is often used to make sure that respondents from different groups are well-represented in the sample. If strata have different behavioural properties, this may lead to smaller standard errors of population estimates. Clustering is often used if, e.g. for monetary reasons, it is inefficient to draw a random sample. The consequence of clustered sampling is that the respondents from the same cluster are not independent from each other. If this is not taken into account, it will lead to underestimation of the standard errors of population estimates. Information at the respondent level on the strata and/or cluster respondents belong to can often be used to take the sampling design features into account and arrive at proper estimates of population characteristics and their standard errors.

If different elements of the population have different probabilities to be included in the sample by design, this may influence both the estimates of population characteristics and their standard errors. Different strata may have (slightly) different selection probabilities, but these probabilities may also differ because of other aspects of the sampling design. For instance, if random dwellings or households are selected as the sampling frame, respondents in small households will be overrepresented and these have to receive relatively smaller weights than respondents in large households. Generally, the design weights take care of these differential selection probabilities.

If some groups in the sample are more or less likely to respond than others, this may also lead to bias in the resulting population estimates. If women respond more often than men, and women have other views than men, not taking this differential probability to participate into account, will lead to biased population estimates. Usually, so-called post-stratification weights are calculated to take differences in response between subgroups into account.

In ESS Round 9, stratification and clustering are taken into account by the variables `strata` (sampling stratum), `psu` (primary sampling cluster), and `prob` (sampling probability). These variables can be used within the `svy` procedure to take the sampling design into account. `svy` can be used in combination with many standard commands, like **mean**, **regress** or **stcox**. Next, a number of weights are constructed. The variable `dweight` provides the design weight, which corrects for different selection probabilities between respondents only. The variable `pspweight` provides the combined effect of correcting for differential design inclusion and post-stratification. Post-stratification occurs on gender, age, region and educational level. Weights are constructed by using the Labour Force Survey (LFS) as the standard to which the ESS realized sample is compared. Finally, the variable `anweight` includes both the design correction, the post-stratification correction and an adjustment for population size. As a result, it can be used in analyses where the relative population size of countries matters. No separate post-stratification weight (without design correction) is available.

In the Appendix, we provide an example of the consequences of not taking the design characteristics and weights into account. It shows that not accounting for different sampling design characteristics can bias the conclusions drawn from the data. If respondents have

different inclusion probabilities as a result of the survey design or response is selective because of different response probabilities, this

will bias the point estimates we are interested in if relevant characteristics are unevenly distributed across the selection. It might also increase the standard errors of these point estimates, thus increasing the risk of making type 1 errors. This latter risk is even larger if the sampling design is not taken into account. Particularly if complex, clustered sampling designs are used, not taking these design effects into account will lead to strong underestimation of the standard errors of point estimates.

Lessons to be learned for the GGS

Given the importance of accounting for the sampling design and of accounting for selective nonresponse, GGS should move towards the model used by the ESS. To do so, information on the sampling design is needed, as well as information on the probability of inclusion in the sample and information on selective non-response. Regarding the latter, ESS calculates post-stratification weights based on age, gender, region and educational level. Given the GGS' focus on demographic processes, and given that there are indications from ongoing analyses that married individuals are more likely to participate in the survey than non-married, it is advisable to also include marital status in the construction of post-stratification weights. It could be that population-level information on educational level and marital status is hard to get by. In those countries, post-stratification weights will only be based on variables for which sufficiently reliable population data are available.

Given that the focus of the GGS, like other international surveys, such as ESS and SHARE, is foremost on making scientifically sound statements about individuals rather than about households, the Central Hub will only calculate individual sampling weights, not household sampling weights.

Information needed to implement the weighting strategy outlined above

To implement the strategy suggested in the previous section, information is needed. Most of that information has to be supplied by the National Teams of the countries in which data are collected. Below, we provide an overview of the data needed.

Information on design weights

1. For all respondents in the dataset, a variable `propincl`, giving the probability of inclusion into the sample for the respective respondent has to be provided.
2. A memo, detailing how these inclusion probabilities have been calculated has to be provided.

Based on these two pieces of information, the Central Hub will examine whether the information is sufficient to calculate the design weights, or whether additional information is needed. Special attention will be paid to the inclusion probabilities from countries that have used a dwelling or household sample, as it needs to be ascertained that differences in inclusion probabilities by household have been taken into account in a proper manner.

Information on post-stratification weights

1. An Excel spreadsheet, providing the most recent reliable information on population figures on five variables of interest have to be provided. These variables are • **Age (A)**, categorized in four groups [18-30, 31-45, 46-60, 61+]¹;
 - **Gender (G)**, categorized as male and female;
 - **Region (R)**, categorized in NUTS1 regions or comparable;
 - **Level of education (L)**, categorized as low [ISCED 0-2], medium [ISCED 3-4] and high [ISCED5+];
 - **Marital status (M)**, categorized as ever married versus never married.

A cross-classification of all five variables is not feasible, as this information is usually not available, and if it is, the distribution of respondents in some cells of the cross-classification may be too low. We would prefer two cross-classifications (AGRL and AGRM). If this is not available, the best possible combination of subclassifications is preferred. E.g., if the cross-classification AGRL is not available the combination AGR + RL is preferred over AGR + L. If no *reliable* information on one or more of the five variables mentioned above is available, information has to be provided only on those variables for which such information is available. In that instance, weights will be calculated based on the factors for which information is available.

2. A memo, detailing the sources of the cross-classified data has to be provided. This should include a quality assessment of the sources.

Based on the provided population figures, the Central Hub will compare the realized distribution in the sample to the distributions based on the population figures. Next, Iterative Proportional

¹ The age range can be adapted in consultation with the Central Hub based on availability and appropriateness of the data in a specific country.

Fitting (IPF) will be used to calculate post-stratification weights that will assure that the distributions in the realized sample optimally mirror the distributions in the population.

Information on sampling design

1. For all respondents in the dataset, a variable `stratum`, providing information on the stratum to which the respective respondent belongs has to be provided. This is true for all countries, where a stratified sample has been drawn.
2. For all respondents in the dataset, a variable `psu`, providing information on the sampling unit to which the respective respondent belongs has to be provided. This is true for all countries, where a clustered sample has been drawn. If a multi-stage cluster procedure has been used, a `psu` variable for each stage has to be provided, e.g. `psu1`, `psu2`, `psu3`.
3. A memo, detailing how the sample has been drawn has to be provided. This should include information on what the sampling frame was, whether (and if so, how) stratification has been used,

and whether (and if so, how) clustering has been used. In the memo, arguments have to be provided for why the choices made are optimal given the sampling situation in the country.

Based on these pieces of information, the Central Hub will examine whether the information is sufficient, or whether additional information is needed. Based on the information, variables will be constructed to allow using the `svy` procedure in Stata (or equivalent procedures in R).

References

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- ESS Data Archive (n.d.). *ESS9 – 2018 Documentation Report, Edition 3.1*. Downloaded from www.europeansocialsurvey.org.
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Appendix: Consequences of (Not) Taking Design Features into Consideration – An Example from the ESS Round 9

In this example, we show the consequences of using different strategies to take sampling features into account. We use data from ESS Round 9. Syntaxes used are presented at the end of this Appendix. Our focus of interest is the variable `alvgptn` (approval of unmarried cohabitation). The question asks “how much do you approve or disapprove if a man (woman) lives with a partner without being married”, and answer categories run from 1 (strongly disapprove) to 5 (strongly approve). We examine the mean score on this variable, by applying the procedure **mean**, and we perform an OLS regression (**regress**) with `alvgptn` as the dependent variable and `gender` (`male`), `gender` used in the split ballot (`sbmale`), years of education (`edyrs`), disinterest in politics (`polintr`), age (`agea`) and never married (`evmar`) as independent variables.

We compare four different approaches to handling design features. The first approach is by ignoring design aspects altogether (NO), the second is by only using design weight (DW), the third is by using both design and post-stratification weights (PW), and the fourth approach is the using design and stratification weights and taking the sampling design into account, by using the `svy` command. We call this the ‘full package’ (FP) approach.

We compare results for two different countries, that strongly differ in their sampling design, viz. Netherlands and Bulgaria. The Netherlands uses data from the population registers and is thus able to draw a simple random sample of individuals. The data are stratified by age, gender and region. Bulgaria uses a list of dwellings enumerated in the 2011 Census and uses a three-stage procedure. In the first stage, census enumeration areas are selected as primary sampling units, using a stratified probability proportionate to size (PPS) design. This leads to 555 PSUs from 78 strata. In the second stage, from each PSU six dwellings were chosen using systematic PPS sampling, with dwellings sorted by size. Finally, within dwellings, respondents are chosen by the first-birthday rule. Based on these differences in sampling procedures, it can be expected that design features will have larger consequences on parameter estimates in Bulgaria than in the Netherlands. Regarding the consequences of taking post-stratification into account, no a priori expectations between Bulgaria and the Netherlands can be made.

Differences in averages

First, the results for the mean estimates of trust in politicians and its standard error are presented in Table 1, separately for the Netherlands and Bulgaria and for the different sampling approaches.

Table 1 Mean and standard error of scores on approval of unmarried cohabitation in the Netherlands and Bulgaria, using different sampling approaches

Sampling approach	Netherlands		Bulgaria	
	Mean	SE	Mean	SE
NO	4.226	.024	3.089	.024
DW	4.227	.024	3.086	.025
PW	4.201	.024	3.158	.026
FP	4.201	.024	3.158	.031

NO = no correction, DW = design weight, PW = design weight + post-stratification weight, FP = design weight + post-stratification weight + correction for sampling design

The results in Table 1 show that for the Netherlands, the differences in mean scores and standard errors between the four approaches are relatively small. Post-stratification leads to slightly lower mean scores but the SEs in all approaches are the same. In Bulgaria, the mean scores also vary little across the four approaches. However, the standard error of the estimated mean increases across the approaches. It is especially large for the FP approach, where it is about 30% larger than in the NO approach (.031 versus .024). This probably reflects the clustered sampling approach which makes the sample much less efficient than an SRS approach. Not taking this into account considerably underestimates the ‘true’ standard error of this mean.

Differences in regression coefficients

Next, we turn to the consequences of design features for regression estimates. The results for the Netherlands are presented in Table 2, for Bulgaria in Table 3.

Table 2 Regression coefficients approval of unmarried cohabitation in the Netherlands, using different sampling approaches (N=1,641)

	B				SE			
	NO	DW	PW	FP	NP	DW	PW	FP
Male	-.107*	-.107*	-.106*	-.106*	.047	.047	.049	.049
Male (split ballot)	-.025	-.025	-.018	-.018	.047	.047	.048	.048
Age	.002	.001	.002	.002	.002	.002	.002	.002
Never married	.251*	.255*	.257*	.257*	.063	.065	.069	.068
Education	.030*	.030*	.029*	.029*	.006	.005	.006	.006
Political disinterest	-.064*	-.065*	-.060	-.060	.031	.032	.033	.033
Constant	3.621*	3.607*	3.586*	3.586*	.204	.225	.237	.235

* $p < .05$

NO = no correction, DW = design weight, PW = design weight + post-stratification weight, FP = design weight + post-stratification weight + correction for sampling design

For the Netherlands (Table 2), particularly post-stratification leads to some change in the regression estimates (b) for approval of unmarried cohabitation. The effect of political disinterest become smaller (and turn from statistically significant at the $p < .05$ level in the NO and DW approach to statistically non-significant in the PW and FP approaches. This suggests that selective non-response correction reduces the estimate for political interest (and for the constant to a lesser extent). Changes in standard errors suggest that not controlling for any aspects of the sampling design slightly underestimates standard errors for most estimates. Finally, correcting for the sampling design is rather unimportant in the Netherlands, probably because non-clustered SRS was used.

Table 3 Regression coefficients for approval of cohabitation in Bulgaria, using different sampling approaches (N=2,019)

	B				SE			
	NO	DW	PW	FP	NP	DW	PW	FP
Male	-.054	-.051	-.053	-.053	.047	.049	.051	.048
Male (split ballot)	.058	.070	.082	.082	.046	.048	.050	.046
Age	-.013*	-.012*	-.012*	-.012*	.002	.002	.002	.002
Never married	.332*	.356*	.295*	.295*	.070	.072	.073	.077
Education	.026*	.027*	.021*	.021*	.006	.006	.006	.007
Political disinterest	-.024	-.048	-.037	-.037	.028	.030	.032	.036
Constant	3.164*	3.144*	3.239*	3.239*	.207	.218	.225	.256

* $p < .05$

NO = no correction, DW = design weight, PW = design weight + post-stratification weight, FP = design weight + post-stratification weight + correction for sampling design

For Bulgaria (Table 3), the consequences for the regression estimates are comparable to the ones in the Netherlands. Changes are rather small, with the exception of the constant. Again, and much stronger than in the Dutch case, the standard errors are affected considerably. For most variables, both applying design weights, applying post-stratification weights and taking the sampling design into account increases the standard errors. In particular, taking the sampling design into account matters a lot, suggesting that not doing so will strongly bias (and often underestimate) standard errors of parameters of interest in countries with sampling designs that differ considerably from SRS.

Stata syntax for the results presented in Tables 1, 2 and 3

```
* In this syntax, the consequences of several weighting approaches on the estimates of
different
* types of analysis is examined
* Data come from ESS Round 9 * This is done for two countries:
* The Netherlands, which has an individual sampling frame with only few strata * Bulgaria,
which has a three stage approach, using a 'poorer' sampling frame
* Compared are (1) no weighting, (2) using combined design-post-stratification weights and (3)
a full * svy approach
```

```
svyset psu [pweight=pspwght], strata(stratum)
generate sbmale=0
if admge==1 replace
sbmale=1 if admge==2
label variable sbmale "split ballot indicator"
label define sbindvl 0 "female version" 1 "male
version" label values sbmale sbindvl tab
sbmale, miss
generate male=0
if gndr==2
replace male=1 if
gndr==1 tab gndr
male
```

```
* Mean of disapproval of unmarried cohabitation is estimated (Table 1)
```

```
svydescribe if ctry=="NL"
```

```
mean alvgptn if ctry=="NL"
mean alvgptn [pweight=dweight] if
ctry=="NL" mean alvgptn
[pweight=pspwght] if ctry=="NL" svy:
mean alvgptn if ctry=="NL"
```

```
svydescribe if ctry=="BG"
```

```
mean alvgptn if ctry=="BG"
mean alvgptn [pweight=dweight] if
ctry=="BG" mean alvgptn
[pweight=pspwght] if ctry=="BG" svy:
mean alvgptn if ctry=="BG"
```

```
* Approval of unmarried cohabitation is regressed on a set of covariates (Tables 2 and 3)
```

```
regress alvgptn male eduysr polintr agea evmar sbmale if ctry=="NL"
regress alvgptn male eduysr polintr agea evmar sbmale [pweight=dweight] if
ctry=="NL" regress alvgptn male eduysr polintr agea evmar sbmale
[pweight=pspwght] if ctry=="NL" svy: regress alvgptn male eduysr polintr agea
evmar sbmale if ctry=="NL"
```

```
regress alvgptn male eduysr polintr agea evmar sbmale if ctry=="BG"
regress alvgptn male eduysr polintr agea evmar sbmale [pweight=dweight] if
ctry=="BG" regress alvgptn male eduysr polintr agea evmar sbmale
[pweight=pspwght] if ctry=="BG" svy: regress alvgptn male eduysr polintr agea
evmar sbmale if ctry=="BG"
```